

Field efficacy of certain chemicals in the control of bacterial blight of rice in the Punjab

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Bacterial blight of rice caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson is a major disease in the tropics. In a field trial during kharif 1976, seedlings of Jaya were inoculated with a virulent isolate of *X. oryzae* 3 wk after transplant. Chemicals were

sprayed four times at fortnightly intervals starting 72 hours after inoculation at the rate of 2 liters/plot. Observations for bacterial blight were recorded 10 days after the last spray (see table).

Less disease was recorded in plots sprayed with copper oxychloride and with Agrimycin-100 + copper sulfate than in the unsprayed check. Agrimycin-100 alone and streptomycin showed little effect. There were no significant differences in yields with the various treatments. The yield of the inoculated control was 25.9% less than that of the uninoculated check.

Relative efficacy of various chemicals in controlling bacterial leaf blight of rice.

Treatment	Concentration	Disease incidence ^a (%) ^b	Yield (t/ha)
Agrimycin-100	200 ppm a.i. ^c	33.85 (31.0)	4.80
Streptomycin	200 ppm a.i. ^c	33.95 (31.2)	4.85
Agrimycin-100 +	200 ppm a.i. ^c	31.23 (26.9)	4.95
Copper sulfate	100 ppm a.i. ^c		
Copper oxychloride	0.2% (Commercial)	29.70 (24.6)	5.05
Inoculated control (water spray)		36.02 (34.6)	4.85
Uninoculated control	—	—	6.55

^aAverage of six replications.

^bC.D. at 5% level = 4.21; C.D. at 1% level = 5.74. Figures in parentheses indicate percent disease index. Others are transformed values and C.D. applies to these only.

^ca.i. = active ingredients.

Antibiotics for control of sheath blight of rice

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Sheath blight of rice caused by *Corticium sasakii* (Shirai) Matsumoto is increasing in severity in certain parts of Tamilnadu because of the introduction of rice strains that are high yielding and responsive to heavy fertilization.

A field trial of eight antibiotics was conducted during the kuruvai (June–September 1975) and the thaladi (October 1975 – January 1976). During its maximum tillering stage the susceptible rice variety ADT-31 was sprayed twice with a 1,000-ppm concentration of Agrimycin-500, Streptomycin, Blastidicin, Polyoxin, Aureofungin,

Tetracycline, Kasumin, or oxytetracycline. All of the treatments reduced the disease incidence; the antifungal antibiotic Aureofungin was highly effective. Increased yield was also recorded from the plots treated with it. ❧

Fungicidal control of sheath blight of rice

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The fungicides Benlate, Dexon Wet, Ceresan, Daconil, Dithane Z-78, Dithane D-14, Kitazin, Hinosan, N.F. 48, Brassicol, Brestan, El-273, thiram, and Demosan in 2% solutions were tested for the control of sheath blight of rice caused by *Corticium sasakii*

(Shirai) Matsumoto. They were sprayed twice during the maximum tillering stage of the susceptible variety ADT-31. Compared with the untreated control, all the test fungicides minimized disease incidence. Benlate, Demosan, Hinosan, Kitazin, and Daconil were found to be highly effective. The treated plots also had significantly higher grain yield than the untreated control. ❧

Root-lesion nematode damage in upland rice

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Observations indicate the potential of the polyphagous nematode *Pratylenchus indicus* as a pest of rice in uplands and in soils where crop rotations with susceptible cereal and fodder grass crops are adopted. In recent surveys on the Central Rice Research Institute farm, the prevalence of the nematode was observed. Direct-seeded rice showed patches of yellowing plants within 15 days of germination. In the following week, leaves wilted and dried up. Mortality was complete at 40 to 50 days after germination (see photograph).

Roots of infested plants showed surface lesions with necrotic cells in the cortex. All the stages of *P. indicus* were observed inside roots. The nematode population increased with plant age and peaked in October 1975 when the crops were heading. The symptoms at that stage were yellowing of leaves in patches, and partial earhead exertion.

Mortality of nematode-infested upland rice at Cuttack, India, 4 to 50 days after germination.